

EDUCATION OF PROFESSIONAL CULTURE OF TEACHERS:
THEORY AND PRACTICAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract: In this article, the professional culture of future pedagogues development issues have been researched. The professional culture of educators is interpreted as a sum of their moral values, behavior culture, responsibility in the process of education, and the ability to implement social relations. Also, the role and importance of these technologies in the training of pedagogic personnel is highlighted. This study includes recommendations aimed at effective organization of the educational process in the field of pedagogy and the formation of a high professional culture in future pedagogues.

Keywords: Professional culture, pedagogical sciences, future pedagogues, moral values, behavior culture, practical training, role-playing games, educational projects, case analysis

In the conditions of today's globalization, in the process of training pedagogues, the formation of their professional culture is of great importance. Professional culture of pedagogues is the sum of their knowledge, skills, professional attitudes aimed at the implementation of social norms and values. The professional culture of teachers means the sum of their knowledge, skills, social norms and values in their professional activities. This culture includes the pedagogue's ability to implement moral values, culture of behavior, responsibility in the educational process, and social relations.

1. Moral values: It is manifested in the teacher's adherence to such principles as humanity, justice, loyalty, compassion, and humanism. He must be loyal to his profession, respectful, and attentive to his students.

2. Culture of treatment:It reflects the teacher's ability to communicate effectively with students, colleagues, and the community. This includes establishing open and respectful relationships with learners and presenting knowledge in a clear and engaging way.

3. Responsibilities in the educational process:It means the pedagogue's responsibility in planning, organizing and carrying out the educational process effectively. This means conducting high-quality classes, constantly monitoring the level of students' knowledge and helping them develop.

4. The ability to implement social relations:It encompasses the teacher's ability to interact with the public and find their place in the professional community. This includes establishing professional contacts, improving their skills, and participating in collaborative projects.

These four components are the main foundation for the formation of the professional culture of pedagogues.

1. It is important to form the professional culture of future pedagogues.

2. The professional culture of teaching staff directly affects their teaching effectiveness. This culture is determined by the teacher's moral values, communication culture, and high responsibility in professional activities. For future teachers, professional culture includes not only theoretical knowledge, but also practical skills.

2. Technologies of formation of professional culture in pedagogical sciences

The following technologies can be used to develop the professional culture of future pedagogues:

- Teaching students based on interactive educational methods;
- Organization of activities that develop creative and critical thinking;
- Providing opportunities for independent learning and self-assessment.

3. Practical experiences and results

Practical exercises, role-playing games, and educational projects are considered effective methods in the formation of professional culture in pedagogical sciences.

The following methods are effective in the formation of professional culture in pedagogical sciences:

1. Practical training: This allows you to apply theoretical knowledge in practice during the training process. Students test their knowledge and skills in situations close to real life, learn to solve pedagogical problems independently.

2. Role-playing: Students take on different roles in different pedagogical situations. For example, they can understand different pedagogical relationships and problems by playing the role of a teacher, student, parent, or administrator.

3. Educational projects: Involves students in independent and creative activities. They work in groups and prepare a project on a certain topic. In this process, professional competence, team work skills and communication culture are developed.

4. Discussions: Provides exchange of ideas between students on ethical and pedagogical issues. It develops critical thinking and reasoning in them.

5. Case analysis (situational tasks): Students are presented with various pedagogical situations and are required to analyze the situation and propose effective solutions.

6. Initiative and creativity: Students are tasked with independently creating new lesson plans, teaching materials, or learning projects. This develops pedagogical creativity and a sense of responsibility in them.

For example, it is possible to form moral values by engaging students in mutual debates and analyzing their attitudes to pedagogical situations.

Developing the professional culture of future teachers is a complex and ongoing process that requires a systematic approach. By developing their knowledge, skills and personal qualities, it is possible to train quality teaching

professionals. The technologies highlighted in this article will help make this process more efficient.

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